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Deliverable Review and Approval

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Done by
1	Initial Review and Comments obtained on the excel file with the list of standards	12/03/2021 – IRIS
2	Technological partners contribution to standards search	12/03/2021 - IRIS 18/03/2021 - CNRS 01/04/2021 - UNITO 24/04/2021 - Fondazione Politecnico
3	Finalization of the deliverable	25/05/2021
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Acronyms and definitions

AREA	When it relates to the state of the art analysis (described in chapter 3), AREA identifies the keyword used to make the search from the UNI/ISO catalogues
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
Circular Economy	Economy that is restorative and regenerative by design, and which aims to keep products, components and materials at their highest utility and value at all times, distinguishing between technical and biological cycles [SOURCE: Adapted from Ellen macarthur Foundation] ISO 20400:2017(en)
Environmental management	Part of the management system used to manage environmental aspects, fulfil compliance obligations, and address risks and opportunities

	ISO 14001:2015(en)
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
Industrial wastewater	Water discharged after being used in, or produced by, an industrial process, and which is of no further immediate value to that process ISO 6107-1:2004(en), 44
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
KEYWORD	When it relates to the state of the art analysis (described in chapter 3), KEYWORD identifies the keyword used to reclassify the content of the standard deliverables
Physical method (of analysis)	Method for the determination of chemical composition in which the determination of composition is carried out without submitting the sample to chemical reaction, for example an optical emission spectrometric method, an X-ray fluorescence spectrometric method. ISO 14284:1996(en), 3.2
Project Life Cycle	It is defined set of phases from the start to the end of the project ISO 21500:2012, 2.12 ISO 10006:2017(en), 3.8
Public administration	Entity, i.e., a Person, which is an organization and has the added attribute of being authorized to act on behalf of a regulator ISO/IEC 15944-1:2011, 3.54 *For the scope of this document, it is mainly linked to procurement.
R&I	Research and Innovation
Requirement	Need or expectation that is stated Note 1 to entry: Specified requirements can be stated in normative documents such as regulations, standards and technical specifications. Note 2 to entry: Specified requirements can be detailed or general. ISO/IEC 17000:2020(en)

Social responsibility	<p>responsibility of an organization for the impacts of its decisions and activities on society and the environment, through transparent and ethical behaviour that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — contributes to sustainable development, including health and the welfare of society; — takes into account the expectations of stakeholders; — is in compliance with applicable law and consistent with international norms of behaviour; and — is integrated throughout the organization and practised in its relationships <p>Note 1 to entry: Activities include products, services and processes.</p> <p>Note 2 to entry: Relationships refer to an organization's activities within its sphere of influence.</p> <p>ISO 26000:2010(en), 2.18</p>
Society	<p>For the scope of this document, it is mainly linked to a range of individuals, groups of people, networks, movements, associations and organizations (of different types) that manifest and advocate for the interests of their members and others. It is mainly linked to the idea of sustainable development.</p> <p>Close to the definition of Civil Society:</p> <p>Wide range of individuals, groups of people, networks, movements, associations and organizations that manifest and advocate for the interests of their members and others</p> <p>Note 1 to entry: It can be based on philanthropic, cultural, religious, environmental or political values and convictions.</p> <p>Note 2 to entry: This definition excludes for-profit companies and businesses, academia and all government-dependent entities.</p> <p>ISO 22300:2021(en), 3.1.31</p>
Soil quality	<p>All current positive or negative properties with regards to soil utilization and soil functions</p> <p>ISO 11074:2015(en), 2.1.15</p>
TC - Technical Committee	<p>Technical committees responsible for developing standards (any type of document)</p>
UNI	<p>Ente Italiano di Normazione (Italian Standardization Body)</p>

Urban areas	For the scope of this document, it is mainly linked to sustainable cities (in particular for KPIs related to water).
Wastewater	Water that has been treated to meet specific water quality requirements for intended beneficial use Note 1 to entry: Examples of treatment technologies include microfiltration, reverse osmosis and/or ultraviolet disinfection. ISO 24513:2019, 3.2.2.3 ISO 46001:2019(en), 3.25
Wastewater service	For the scope of this document, it is mainly linked to management of assets of water supply and wastewater systems.
Water quality	Physical (e.g. thermal), chemical and biological characteristics of water with respect to its suitability for an intended use by humans or ecosystems ISO 14050:2020(en), 3.10.10
Water reuse	Use of treated wastewater for beneficial use Note 1 to entry: Synonymous also to water reclamation ISO 20670:2018(en), 3.84

Foreword¹

If we see our Planet from space, it appears like a 'blue ball' due to the predominance of water on it. Nevertheless, water is a scarce and unevenly distributed resource.

Globally, most water is used for agricultural activities, but significant volumes of water are also consumed for industrial activities and by households in developed countries.

Improving water management policies has become a global imperative: United Nations 6th global goal for sustainable development is to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all².

In the coming years, global demand for water will increase dramatically: the primary sector will be called upon to meet the nutritional needs of a larger population that will also have changed its eating habits.

Better management of water resources is necessary and possible, but to reach it, it is essential to adequately invest in infrastructure, research and technology. This starts with simple concepts such as the renovation of water pipes, the use of micro-irrigation, the possibility of using crops that are resistant to different chemical and physical characteristics of water and the use of desalination.

A very important role in this particular scenario will be played by standardisation. Standards developed by national, European and international technical committees will help the world of research and innovation to make project

¹ For more information: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/it/segnali/segnali-2018/articoli/acqua-pulita-significa-vita-salute>

² <https://www.globalgoals.org/>

results applicable to the market needs, current technologies and regulations. Furthermore, knowledge of standards will support market entry and will facilitate interoperability.

Executive summary

This deliverable aims at informing a heterogeneous public about the standardization activities that have been carried out by UNI for Project Ô.

This document will first provide the necessary knowledge on the “standardization landscape” in order to let the reader be more conscious about the actors, the documents and the binomial standards-innovation that have been the subject of webinars and trainings that UNI carried out for Project Ô partners. This will possibly raise the public awareness of the impact that standardization may have on R&I projects in promoting interoperability, compliance of project results to standards, and avoiding duplication of existing knowledge.

In the first paragraph it is synthetically described Project Ô and the role that UNI has within it.

Then, the reader will dive into the “standardization world”, to understand its potential role as innovation and technology transfer booster (Chap. 2): this is in order to transfer also to a wider public the information already given to the project partners during the workshops organized by UNI to provide them a common general knowledge of the standardisation system.

Afterwards, the document will provide a first informative sum-up on the preliminary state of the art analysis of standardization documents at Italian, EU and international level, that are potentially relevant in the context of Project Ô (Chap. 3). The section deepens the methodology and the steps followed to identify existing standards related to water and water management, or linked to some technologies used in the context of Project Ô and potentially useful for implementing the project collaborative platform and/or supporting further actions related to possible future inputs coming from the project. Some standardization gaps, that have already been identified, will be introduced in this chapter.

Chapter 4 will introduce the next activities that UNI may carry out for Project Ô.

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1. Introduction: Project Ô and the role of UNI

Project Ô³ is a European project funded under the framework programme Horizon 2020 with grant agreement No 776816. It has started on 1st June 2018 with the aim to demonstrate approaches and technologies to drive an integrated and symbiotic use of water within a specific area, putting together the needs of different users and waste water producers, involving regulators, service providers, civil society, industry and agriculture.

The project seeks to apply the pillars of integrated water management (IWM) as a model for “water planning” (akin to spatial planning) and to demonstrate low cost, modular technologies that can be easily retrofitted into any water management infrastructure at district/plant level, hence enabling even small communities and SMEs to implement virtuous practices.

Figure 1 Circular Economy Platform (CEP)⁴

Technologies and planning instruments complement each other as the first make possible the second and the latter can provide as example or even prescribe the former (and similar technologies allowing virtuous water use practices). Indeed, the technologies support the regulators in implementing policy instruments, as foreseen by IWM, for convincing stakeholders (like developers and industry) to implement water efficiency strategies and could include instruments for e.g. rewarding virtuous behaviours (for example: advantageous water tariffs), planning regulations that award planning consent more swiftly or even prescribe the use of water from alternative sources (including recycling). Project Ô has in summary the overall objective of providing stakeholders (everybody using or regulating the use of water in an area) with a toolkit that enables them to plan the use of and utilise the resource water whatever its history and provenance, obtaining significant energy savings in terms of avoided treatment of water and waste water and release of pressure (quantity abstracted and pollution released) over green water sources. This overall objective will be demonstrated in up to four sites each in different Countries of Europe and in Israel, involving industries, aquaculture and agriculture as well as local authorities of different sizes.⁵

Below, few words about the four demo-sites (source: <http://eu-project-o.eu/>).

³ <http://eu-project-o.eu/>

⁴ Source: <http://eu-project-o.eu/>

⁵ Source: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776816>

<p>Lecce, Italy With more than 4 million inhabitants, Puglia Region is situated on the south-eastern tip of Italy and is one of the most popular tourist destinations in Europe. The circular water module ADV.ERT will be located in the city of Lecce, specifically, in a well, Pozzo Guardati, which needs to be recovered in terms of water quality.</p>	<p>Eilat, Israel A city of over 50,000 inhabitants, Eilat is the southern city of Israel and a popular tourist resort situated at the Red Sea. In this demo-site, Project Ô will implement a mobile circular water plant, SALTECH, in a mariculture farm. Mariculture has a big potential to provide high-quality food in a sustainable way in Israel and the rest of the world.</p>	<p>Almendralejo, Spain Almendralejo is a home for almost 35,000 inhabitants. The town is known by its wines and the table olive production. For this demo-site, Project Ô is developing a mobile water treatment technology, MOBILE3TECH, based on the degradation of toxic organic pollutants through the use of solar light. This will allow to increase irrigation and urban water use efficiency.</p>	<p>Omiš, Croatia With a population of around 15,000 people, Omiš is settled in Croatian region of Dalmatia right at the place where the Cetina River enters the Adriatic Sea. The main goal in this demo-site is to implement circular water technology based on photocatalysis within the production process of the textile company Galeb d.d., whose main activity is the production of wearing apparel such as underwear, outerwear and nightwear.</p>

UNI's role within the project is to spot existing relevant standard at national, European and International level in order to carry out a **first state of the art analysis**. Starting from the standards identified, and supported by partners' expertise, **relevant standardization gaps** will be recognized and **actions** will be put in place in order to contribute to possibly act to fill in these gaps or, at least, inform relevant technical committees, at national, European and international level about their existence. This work is possible only through the essential contribution of all the project partners.

At the same time, UNI has sought to increase the awareness in the importance of standardization in research and innovation projects as a mean to bridge the gap between the innovation and the market. In this direction, UNI has organised several webinars and workshops (training sessions) about the world of standardisation either reserved only to project partners or opened to all.

2. The Standardization world

One of the goals of Project Ô is to strengthen the relationship between R&I and standardisation for the development of innovative technologies for sustainable water management systems. Also important is the dissemination of circular economy approaches and best practices in water planning, management and re-use.

So standardisation is an integral component of the entire project life cycle, acting as tool to transfer knowledge in a co-creation process which is typical of the standardisation system.

To better understand what standardization is, in this chapter it will be presented a summary of the entire system, in order to have a clear framework of the underpinning principles, the actors on the stage, the documents produced and the binomial standards-innovation.

2.1 Standardization System

The Standardization system is structured in “different layers or levels”, starting from the national one, up to the European and International level. The three different levels, which correspond to different standardization bodies, are strictly connected and are based on the principle of avoiding duplication and overlapping.

At European level the standardization system is defined and regulated by the EU Regulation 1025/2012⁶, in which the European Parliament and the Council addressed standardization by defining its role, underlying the aspect of being able to “boost the competitiveness of enterprises by facilitating the free movement of goods and services, network interoperability, means of communication, technological development and innovation.” In addition to this, Standardization is seen as an important tool for supporting innovation, since it facilitates the transfer of R&I results to the market.

As the abovementioned Regulation states, “the primary objective of standardisation is the definition of voluntary technical or quality specifications with which current or future products, production processes or services may comply. Standardisation can cover various issues, such as standardisation of different grades or sizes of a particular product or technical specifications in product or services markets where compatibility and interoperability with other products or systems are essential”. So standards may be related to products, materials, services, organisations, processes, while addressing safety, quality, performance, interoperability, requirements, etc.

In short, standards can cover every aspect of the economic and social activities. The figure below offers a visual example.

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32012R1025>

Figure 2 - Standardization landscape⁷

In all its applications, standardization aims at supporting economic activity at 360°, boosting productivity, increasing trade within the European Single Market (and beyond) and facilitating businesses (of all sizes) to access the markets. Standards may be important tools to support also SMEs competitiveness.

The benefits of standardization stem from the values and leading principles underpinning it: consensus, openness, transparency, national commitment and technical coherence.

Let's now have a look at the actors on the stage working in the standardization world.

The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC)⁸ are two private European non-profit organisations. Their mission is to support the needs of the market and of the different stakeholders, such as industry and commerce, service providers, public authorities and regulators, academia and research centres, European trade associations and interest groups representing environmentalists, consumers, trade unions as well as small and medium enterprises, and other public and private institutions.

Their aim is also to promote a unique European Standardization System and its results, leading the implementation of best practice in Standardization around the world. With this specific regard, CEN and CENELEC support international Standardization and cooperate closely with the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO)⁹ and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)¹⁰.

CEN and CENELEC communities include 34 National members (Standardization Bodies) who represent CEN and CENELEC in their country, and their country in CEN and CENELEC. A National Standardization Body is the one stop shop for all stakeholders and is the main focal point of access to the concerted system, which comprises regional (European) and international (ISO) standardization.

⁷ Source: Validation Report on Standardization Harmonisation, October 2019

⁸ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/aboutus/Mission/Pages/default.aspx>

⁹ <http://www.iso.org/>

¹⁰ <http://www.iec.ch/>

Figure 3 CEN and CENELEC members

Table 1. List of the 34 CEN National Members¹¹

Acronym	Country	Organization	Website
AFNOR	France	Association Française de Normalisation	www.afnor.org
ASI	Austria	Austrian Standards International - Standardization and Innovation	www.austrian-standards.at
ASI	Austria	Austrian Standards International - Standardization and Innovation	www.austrian-standards.at
ASRO	Romania	Romanian Standards Association	www.asro.ro
BDS	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Institute for Standardization	www.bds-bg.org
BDS	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Institute for Standardization	www.bds-bg.org
BSI	United Kingdom	British Standards Institution	www.bsigroup.com
CYS	Cyprus	Cyprus Organization for Standardisation	www.cys.org.cy
DIN	Germany	Deutsches Institut für Normung	www.din.de
DS	Denmark	Dansk Standard	www.ds.dk
EVS	Estonia	Non-profit Association Estonian Centre for Standardisation and Accreditation	www.evs.ee
HZN	Croatia	Croatian Standards Institute	www.hzn.hr
ILNAS	Luxembourg	Organisme Luxembourgeois de Normalisation	www.portail-qualite.lu
IPQ	Portugal	Instituto Português da Qualidade	http://www1.ipq.pt/
ISRSM	Republic of North Macedonia	Standardization Institute of the Republic of North Macedonia	http://www.isrsm.gov.mk/en
ISS	Serbia	Institute for Standardization of Serbia	www.iss.rs
IST	Iceland	Icelandic Standards	www.stadlar.is

¹¹ Source: <https://standards.cen.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CENWEB:5>

LST	Lithuania	Lithuanian Standards Board	www.lsd.lt
LVS	Latvia	Latvian Standard Ltd.	www.lvs.lv
MCCAA	Malta	The Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority	https://www.mccaa.org.mt/
MSZT	Hungary	Hungarian Standards Institution	www.mszt.hu
NBN	Belgium	Bureau de Normalisation/Bureau voor Normalisatie	www.nbn.be
NBN	Belgium	Bureau de Normalisation/Bureau voor Normalisatie	www.nbn.be
NEN	Netherlands	Nederlands Normalisatie-instituut	www.nen.nl
NQIS/ELOT	Greece	National Quality Infrastructure System	www.elot.gr
NSAI	Ireland	National Standards Authority of Ireland	www.nsaie.ie
PKN	Poland	Polish Committee for Standardization	www.pkn.pl
SFS	Finland	Suomen Standardisoimisliitto r.y.	www.sfs.fi
SIS	Sweden	Swedish Institute for Standards - SIS	www.sis.se
SIST	Slovenia	Slovenian Institute for Standardization	www.sist.si
SN	Norway	Standards Norway	www.standard.no/
SNV	Switzerland	Schweizerische Normen-Vereinigung	www.snv.ch
TSE	Turkey	Turkish Standards Institution	www.tse.org.tr
UNE	Spain	Asociación Española de Normalización	www.une.org
UNI	Italy	Ente Italiano di Normazione	www.uni.com
UNMS SR	Slovakia	Slovak Office of Standards Metrology and Testing	www.unms.sk
UNMZ	Czech Republic	Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing	www.unmz.cz

CEN and CENELEC communities include a network of more than 200.000 experts¹² coming from different countries and from several types of stakeholders, i.e. industry and commerce; service providers; consumers, environmental and societal organisations; research centres and academia; public authorities and regulators; and other public and private institutions.

These experts work to produce European standards – or more generally standardization deliverables – that are market-driven and voluntary documents. They are developed through a transparent, balanced and consensus-based process in which relevant stakeholders are involved, with the aim to produce high-quality technical documents for products, materials, services, organisations and processes. Standards may deal with: quality, safety, security, interoperability, performance, accessibility, environmental requirements...

The European Standardization system is structured and organised in different Technical Committees (TCs), dealing with specific issues (e.g. CEN/TC 230 Water analysis), and that can be subdivided in Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs), according to the complexity of the areas of interest to be addressed. These TCs are included, with their respective mirror committees or working groups, in the structure of the different Standardization Organisations (National, European and International), with their respective mirror committees.

The coherence of the European Standardization system is based on the fact that it is the responsibility of the CEN National Members to implement European Standards as national standards. The National Standardization Bodies distribute and sell the implemented European Standard and have to withdraw any conflicting national standards.

¹² <https://www.cencenelec.eu/aboutus/Communities/Pages/default.aspx>

Moreover, there are specific agreements between the European and International Standardization Organisations (e.g. CEN and ISO) signed to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allows the development and adoption in parallel of the respective standards, with the same content and identification code. The technical collaboration between CEN and ISO was formalised in 1991 in the Vienna Agreement.

In this context, UNI is the Italian Standardization body and represents Italy in CEN and ISO. It is a private, non-profit association founded in 1921 appointed by the Italian government and the European Union to develop, approve and publish technical standards in all economic sectors (industry, trade and services) except for the electric and electro-technical ones. Like all National Standardization Bodies, UNI is also a meeting point between different stakeholders, such as the business world, research institutions, public administrations, universities, education and training authorities, consumers and society.

UNI counts around 4.200 associated entities and a total number of 7.800 experts participating in the standardization activities ¹³.

The Italian standardisation system includes also 7 affiliated entities (Enti Federati), which are associations working in close cooperation and on behalf of UNI in some specific areas:

- CIG (Comitato Italiano Gas) – gas industry
- CTI (Comitato Termotecnico Italiano) – energy industry
- CUNA (Commissione Tecnica di Unificazione nell'Autoveicolo) – automotive industry
- UNICHIM (Associazione per l'Unificazione nel settore dell'Industria Chimica) – chemistry industry
- UNINFO (Tecnologie Informatiche e loro applicazioni) – IT industry
- UNIPLAST (Ente Italiano di Unificazione nelle Materie Plastiche) – plastic industry
- UNSIDER (Ente Italiano di Unificazione Siderurgica) – iron and steel industry

Amongst the National Members, UNI represents the 3° Member in the European Union for number of all CEN and CENELEC active secretariats of Technical Bodies producing standards or other deliverables.

Chart 1 - CEN and CENELEC - Active Secretariats per Country¹⁴

¹³ Data as of February 2021.

¹⁴ Chart elaborated on data as of 27.05.2021 from https://www.cenelec.eu/stats/CEN_CENELEC_in_figures_quarter.htm

2.2 Standardization Documents

According to EU Regulation 1025/2012, a standard is “a technical specification, adopted by a recognised Standardization body, for repeated or continuous application, with which compliance is not compulsory”. So standards and the other standardization deliverables are voluntary technical documents developed by a specific technical body – a Technical Committee (TC), a Working group (WG), a Subcommittee (SC) or a CEN Workshop (CEN/WS).

There are different kinds of standardization deliverables (standards, technical specifications, technical reports and workshops agreements) with peculiar characteristics and that can be developed at national, European or international level.

Table 2: Standardization deliverables

Level	Standard	Technical Specification	Technical Report	Workshop Agreement
International standard	ISO IEC	ISO/TS IEC/TS	ISO/TR IEC/TR	IWA
European Standard	EN	CEN/TS CLC/TS	CEN/TR CLC/TR	CWA
National Standard	UNI, DIN, NF, UNE, etc. UNI EN, DIN EN, etc. UNI ISO, DIN ISO UNI EN ISO, DIN EN ISO	UNI CEN/TS, DIN CEN/TS, etc.	UNI CEN/TR, DIN CEN/TR, etc.	Can vary from country to country
Main characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time for elaboration: 3 years • 2 steps for approval • At EU level: compulsory national adoption Revision: every 5y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time for elaboration: 21 months • 1 step for approval or internal approval in TC • At EU level: optional national adoption Revision: at 3y (upgrading to EN or cancellation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time for elaboration: not binding • Internal approval in TC • At EU level: optional national adoption No revision required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time for elaboration: not binding (around 10-12 months) • Internal approval in the Workshop • At EU level: optional national adoption Revision: at 3y (upgrading to EN or cancellation)

Here below an example of a standard to understand how to interpret the identification code:

Figure 5 – How to read a standard

The typical development process of an EN and ISO standard is described in the following scheme:

Figure 6 – The process to develop a standard¹⁵

2.3 Standardization & Innovation

Standardization is a valuable tool to support and boost innovation as it can create a solid framework to let the market understand and accept innovative solutions. Indeed, standardization documents can help to bridge the gap between research, innovation and global market by building customer trust and confidence in innovative solutions enabling faster mass-market adoption of new technologies, products and services.

European Framework Programmes like Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe pay great attention to the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting and implementing EU policies, and to address global challenges. Within this objective it is strategic to foster the cooperation and communication between the R&I world and the standardization system.

Many funding calls under the Framework Programmes explicitly request projects to contribute to standardization because it helps to:

- disseminate R&I results to industry, society and public administrations;
- facilitate market acceptance by enabling interoperability and compatibility of innovative solutions with existing products, services, systems and processes;
- facilitate trade by diminishing technical barriers;
- facilitate technology transfer;
- support networking between different stakeholders, including scientific and commercial collaborators.

¹⁵ Source: UNI internal document

Moreover, thanks to the agreements in place between CEN, CENELEC, ISO and IEC the results of the R&I projects can be recognised simultaneously at European and international.

The figure beneath visually explains the various links between R&I and standardization.

Figure 7 - An Integrated Approach: Standardization at the Service of Research and Innovation¹⁶

3. Water standards: a preliminary state of the art analysis

From the beginning of the project it was clear that a huge number of standards¹⁷ related to water would have been potentially relevant for the project and also important to take into account both for the technologies implemented in the demo-sites and the development of the collaborative platform.

As highlighted in the previous chapter, basically every aspect of the economic and social activities may be covered by standards. But, while it is highly probable that what you are looking for is somehow covered by a standard, spotting the right one is not always an easy task.

Why? Because technical documents are really complex and the semantic search from catalogues not always give the exact answer.

Just to make an example, if someone searches on the ISO Online Browsing Platform¹⁸ for standards containing the word “water”, she/he will obtain 9,503 results. If one makes a similar search on the UNI catalogue¹⁹ (that includes also ISO standards), looking just for UNI+ISO documents that are current (i.e. not withdrawn), the result is better, but not that much: the number of standards spotted reaches 2,637.

It is easily understandable that not all these documents are probably relevant for the sake, for example, of Project Ô activities.

For all these reasons, after having taught to project partners about the “standardization world”, the second building block of UNI standardization activities within Project Ô has been focused on trying to spot the most relevant current national, European and International standards that may be (potentially) relevant for the project.

In this chapter it will be described the methodology implemented and the preliminary results obtained.

¹⁶ Source: Standards + Innovation 2020

¹⁷ For the scope of this chapter the word “standard” will be used to refer generically to all possible “standard deliverables” as described in the previous chapter.

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#home>

¹⁹ <http://store.uni.com/catalogo/catalogsearch/advanced/>

3.1 Methodology

UNI has chosen to develop a preliminary state of the art analysis starting from a search from its online catalogue²⁰ that gathers overall more than 22.000 standards at national, European (since, as stated in the previous chapter, UNI, as a National Standardization Body, must take in EN standards) and International level (since UNI catalogue is linked to the ISO one).

The methodology implemented can be summarized in four steps as indicated in the chart below:

Chart 2 – Standardization state of the art analysis: the methodology

First of all, some general keywords have been chosen, then it has been run a search of the current (i.e. not withdrawn) standards from the online UNI catalogue, using the option “search by keyword” that let spot the documents in the catalogue which have the keywords either mentioned in the “standard code”, or in the “title”, or in the “summary” field, which reflects the scope of the standard.

For some keywords the number of standards spotted was really relevant (higher than 100), so in order to reduce the number of documents to focus the attention on, a first screen has been carried out directly from the catalogue: having a look at the titles, it is sometimes possible to quickly cancel a standard from the list of the potentially relevant ones (for example, if one searches for “water quality”, the catalogue identifies also the standard “UNI EN 12953-10:2005 Shell boilers - Part 10: Requirements for feedwater and boiler water quality” that is not relevant for Project Ô aimed at implementing an integrated circular approach in water management).

The remaining standards that needed to be checked “more closely” have been collected in an excel file and they have been checked one-by-one (looking at the title and the summary, where publicly available) in order to choose to keep it or not.

Finally, just the potentially relevant standards have been “reclassified” with one or more keywords that may help in spotting easily the content of the document. These keywords have been identified looking at the title and the summary of the documents (not the content, protected by copyright and not publicly accessible). The idea under this activity is to apply a “rough” business intelligence approach to lay the foundation for the next standardization activities (see chapter 4).

The standards that have been deemed potentially relevant for the project have been collected in an excel file where for each document it has been reported:

- Standard Code and title (with the link to retrieve it from the UNI/ISO catalogue)
- Year
- Scope, i.e. a summary (where publicly available) of the content of the document

²⁰ <http://store.uni.com/catalogo/catalogsearch/advanced/>

- Area, i.e. the keywords used for the search
- Keywords, i.e. the #hashtags potentially useful to easily spot the contents of the standards
- UNI / CEN / ISO Technical committee relevant for the document

The focal point of this approach, that is important to highlight, is its adaptive nature: the choice of the keywords is not trivial at all, and the choice to keep or not a standard in the analysis is not easy at all. The feedbacks from the partners and the pooling of partners' expertise is essential for the success of these activities.

For these reasons, UNI will keep to collect project partners' feedbacks and update its analysis accordingly.

Considering that Project Ô is a complex project and that standards may relate to several aspects, the analysis of the standardization state of the art has been split in 3 main topics:

1. General aspects related to "water"
2. Technologies implemented in the project
3. Collaborative platform

For all these three topics the same methodology described in this paragraph was applied and the next session illustrates the main outcomes.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 General aspects related to "water"

For the first topic, the search was focused on 10 general keywords that have been initially deemed useful to spot the "water standards" potentially relevant for Project Ô. They are indicated in this paragraph as "Areas" and their precise definition can be retrieved from the list of acronyms and definitions in this document.

They are indicated as "areas" to distinguish them from the "keywords" of detail that have been chosen to reclassify potentially relevant standards.

The figure below summarizes for each Area the number of standards spotted from the UNI catalogue and the ones that (from a first analysis run by UNI) were deemed potentially relevant for the project.

Area	Number of standards deemed potentially relevant*	Number of standards resulting from UNI catalogue search**
Environmental management	11	88
Industrial waste water	3	25
Public administration	1	7
Society	3	7
Soil quality	3	278
Urban areas	4	16
Waste water service	15	16
Water quality	68	618
Water reuse	12	22
Physical method	3	12
Total number of standards	123	

* the standards included in this list have been selected from a first analysis run by UNI (does not include partners' feedbacks).

** some standards may be counted more than once; this is why the total has not been reported.

Figure 8 – Search for general aspects related to "water": first results

The list of all these 123 standards firstly spotted by UNI has been included in Appendix 1. To these standards, it has to be added also the [UNI ISO 46001 Water efficiency management systems - Requirements with guidance](#) that has been recently published in the UNI catalogue (May 2021).

After a first screen of potential relevant standards, the file excel was shared with some project partners to collect their feedbacks.

From this confrontation, the number of potentially relevant standard fell to 1/3 (from 123 to 46). This is a practical example of the effects of the adaptive approach described in the previous paragraph.

Looking closely to these 46 standards, the technical committees relevant for these documents are:

- [CEN/TC 230 – water analysis](#);
- [CEN/TC 165 – waste water engineering](#).

These CEN TCs were already spotted before the start of the project, but the analysis has spotted also:

- [ISO/TC 147 - water quality](#) and in particular its SC1 (terminology), SC2 (Physical, chemical and biochemical methods), SC6 (sampling);
- [ISO/TC 224 - Service activities relating to drinking water supply wastewater and stormwater systems](#);
- [ISO/TC 282 – water reuse](#) and all its SC (SC 1 - Treated wastewater reuse for irrigation; SC 2 Water reuse in urban areas; SC 3 - Risk and performance evaluation of water reuse system; SC 4 - Industrial water reuse);
- [ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment](#);
- [ISO/TC 268 - Sustainable cities and communities](#);
- [ISO/TMBG - Technical Management Board – groups](#).

Understanding which are the technical committees for relevant standards is necessary to step-up in the standardization activities. Spotting them with a bottom-up approach (starting from the technical documents) looks better to catch market needs.

Looking more deeply at the content of the potentially relevant standards, the three most frequent keywords (proxy of the more relevant topics) appear to be “LCA” for what concerns environmental management; “sampling” for water quality; and “KPI” for services, society/urban areas:

Area and keywords	Number of standards
Environmental management	9
Laboratory	1
LCA	5
Products	1
Waste water	1
Water reuse	1
Industrial waste water	3
Classification	1
Desalination	1
Pilot treatment technology	1
Society	1
KPI	1
Urban areas	3
KPI	2
Municipality	1
Waste water service	7
Crisis management	2
Drinking water	2
KPI	2
Terminology	1
Water quality	14
Carbon dioxide	1
Drinking water	1
Methodology / test methods	1
Organic carbon	1
Performance evaluation	1
Sampling	8
Terminology	1
Water reuse	9
Decentralized water reuse	1
Environmental performance	1
Health risk	1
Industrial cooling system	1
Irrigation	2
Performance evaluation	1
Terminology	1
Water quality	1
Total number of standards	46

Figure 9 – Search for general aspects related to “water”: keywords of potentially relevant standards

3.2.2 Technologies

An ad hoc analysis was run also to spot the relevant standards related to the technologies implemented in the project.

In order to identify the most suitable “areas”, i.e. the words to make the search from the catalogue, UNI contacted the technological partners to ask for their contribution.

Overall, considering all the technologies, UNI has searched standards in 13 Areas, 166 standards came up.

UNI has made a first analysis on the potential relevance of these standards for the technologies implemented in Project Ô, and screened 46 standards. They have been reclassified using keywords that may help in identifying more quickly the documents’ content. In the Appendix 2, it is reported the list of these 46 standards.

The next essential step will be to return to partners to hone this analysis.

Below, some figures summarize the results: what has been obtained from the search from the UNI catalogue and the result of the analysis, split by technology.

Figure 10 – State of the art analysis – topic “technology”: focus on High-voltage generator

Figure 11 – State of the art analysis – topic “technology”: focus on Advanced carbon adsorption & Photocalysis

* Not useful because from UNI catalogue result both standards with "membrane" and "distillation" words, not just the ones with "membrane distillation". It happens also in the ISO catalogue. Further analysis is needed.

Figure 12 – State of the art analysis – topic “technology”: focus on Membrane distillation and nanofiltration

* None apparently related to denitrification, 5 generically related to water quality. Further analysis is needed.

Figure 13 – State of the art analysis – topic “technology”: focus on Bio-algae denitrification

This first tentative analysis that needs to be adjusted after partners' inputs, has also highlighted some potentially relevant technical committees at ISO but also Italian level that enrich the list reported in the previous paragraph (3.2.1):

- [ISO/TC 190/SC 4 \(soil quality\) Biological characterization](#)
- [UNI/CT 004 Environment](#)
- [UNI/CT 027 Metrology](#)
- UNI/CT 033/GL 01 Photocatalysis
- UNI/CT 406/GL 03 Soil quality
- UNI/CT 410 Water quality and its GL 02 Biological methods co-ordination group

Although this is just a first analysis, from the confrontation with some “technological partners” some gaps in the existing standards have already been identified (for example related to the application of some technologies to wastewater treatment).

These aspects will be further analysed, in order to identify the next most suitable actions to contribute to try to close these gaps.

3.2.3 Platform

A state of art analysis on the current standards will be run also related to the platform. Currently, the feedback from the relevant partners have been collected and the areas for carrying out the search have been identified:

- Open and Big data (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42)
- Cloud and Edge computing (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38)
- Privacy and security
- Accessibility (UNI EN 301549:2020)
- Exchange protocols
- Ontology and metadata

4. Conclusions: standardization activities next steps

Diving into the standards world may be a challenge given its complexity. But the benefits that R&I projects can have during the entire life of the project outweigh the costs.

UNI first objective in Project Ô is and will be to raise the awareness in the implications that standardization can have in transferring to the market, even beyond the project duration, the results coming from R&I projects. This has been done through various training activities and will be done also through other dissemination activities.

The second objective is to come up with a framework of the current state of the art in terms of the relevant standards for Project Ô. What has been illustrated in this document (chapter 3 and appendix 1 and 2) will be deepened and will be translated in a toolkit publicly accessible online that (based on the reclassification with keywords of the relevant standards) will make more user-friendly the standard search. Something similar has already been realized by UNI for another H2020 project²¹.

The state of the art analysis will pave the way to the next step of needs identification. A survey will be distributed to all partners to systematically collect their needs and contribute to identify the gaps in the current standards.

On the basis of the previous steps, there will be identified the best actions to take in order to step up and contribute where possible to close the standardization gaps identified.

One activity (for which it is relevant the identification of the technical committees) may probably be the presentation of Project Ô to relevant technical committees. This will contribute to the dissemination to a relevant and expert audience of the project results and best practices in terms of water planning, management and re-use.

All the steps will converge possibly in a CEN workshop agreement (whose realization must comply with CEN rules), a pre-standardization document, or if it not possible, in a strategic standardization roadmap.

Chart 3 – Project Ô: the standardization activities

²¹ <https://www.reclaim-project.eu/standardisation-toolkit/>. RECLAIM has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°869884.

Appendix 1 - List of the standards (123) firstly spotted for the topic "general aspects related to water [section 3.2.1]

TITLE	AREA	KEYWORDS
UNI EN ISO 11274:2020 Soil quality - Determination of the water-retention characteristic - Laboratory methods	Soil quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 13161:2020 Water quality - Polonium 210 - Test method using alpha spectrometry	Water quality	Polonium
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 5667-6:2020 Water quality - Sampling - Part 6: Guidance on sampling of rivers and streams	Water quality	Sampling
UNI EN ISO 11133:2020 Microbiology of food, animal feed and water - Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media	Water quality	Microbiological examination
UNI EN ISO 22908:2020 Water quality - Radium 226 and Radium 228 - Test method using liquid scintillation counting	Water quality	Radium 226
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Radium 228
UNI EN ISO 13165-1:2020 Water quality - Radium-226 - Part 1: Test method using liquid scintillation counting	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Radium 226
UNI EN ISO 13165-2:2020 Water quality - Radium-226 - Part 2: Test method using emanometry	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Radium 226
UNI EN ISO 13165-3:2020 Water quality - Radium-226 - Part 3: Test method using coprecipitation and gamma-spectrometry	Water quality	Radium 226
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN 14451:2020 Devices to prevent pollution by backflow of potable water - In-line anti-vacuum valves DN 10 to DN 50 inclusive - Family D, type A	Environmental management	Drinking water
	Environmental management	Anti vacuum valve
ISO 21793:2020 Water quality — Determination of total organic carbon (TOC), dissolved organic carbon (DOC), total bound nitrogen (TNb), dissolved bound nitrogen (DNb), total bound phosphorus (TPb) and dissolved bound phosphorus (DPb) after wet chemical ca	Water quality	Organic carbon
	Water quality	Nitrogen
	Water quality	Phosphorus
ISO/TS 24541:2020 Service activities relating to drinking water supply, wastewater and stormwater systems -- Guidelines for the implementation of continuous monitoring systems for drinking water quality and operational parameters in drinking water distrib	Water quality	Drinking water
ISO 23070:2020 Water Reuse in Urban Areas — Guidelines for reclaimed water treatment: Design principles of a RO treatment system of municipal wastewater	Urban areas	Municipality
	Urban areas	Terminology
UNI EN ISO 13164-1:2020 Water quality - Radon-222 - Part 1: General principles	Water quality	Radon 222
UNI EN ISO 13164-2:2020 Water quality - Radon-222 - Part 2: Test method using gamma-ray spectrometry	Water quality	Radon 222
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 13164-4:2020 Water quality - Radon-222 - Part 4: Test method using two-phase liquid scintillation counting	Water quality	Radon 222
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
ISO 13166:2020 Water quality — Uranium isotopes — Test method using alpha-spectrometry	Water quality	Uranium
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
ISO 22449-1:2020 Use of reclaimed water in industrial cooling systems — Part 1: Technical guidelines	Water reuse	Industrial cooling system
ISO 23044:2020 Guidelines for softening and desalination of industrial wastewater for reuse	Industrial waste water	Desalination
	Industrial waste water	Softening
UNI EN ISO 22125-1:2020 - Water quality - Technetium-99 - Part 1: Test method using liquid scintillation counting	Water quality	Technetium-99
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
ISO 23056:2020 Water reuse in urban areas — Guidelines for decentralized/onsite water reuse system — Design principles of a decentralized/onsite system	Water reuse	Decentralized water reuse
	Urban areas	Onsite water reuse
ISO 21863:2020 Water quality — Determination of alkylmercury compounds in water — Method using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) after phenylation and solvent extraction	Water quality	Alkylmercury
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
ISO 20304-1:2020 Fine bubble technology — Water treatment applications — Part 1: Test method for evaluating ozone fine bubble water generating systems by the decolorization of methylene blue	Waste water service	Methodology / test methods
	Waste water service	Ozone fine bubble
ISO 24261-1:2020 Fine bubble technology — Elimination method for sample characterization — Part 1: Evaluation procedure	Waste water service	Fine bubble technology
ISO/TR 23015:2020 Fine bubble technology — Measurement technique matrix for the characterization of fine bubbles	Waste water service	Fine bubble technology
UNI EN ISO 22017:2020 Water quality - Guidance for rapid radioactivity measurements in nuclear or radiological emergency situation	Water quality	Radioactivity measurements
	Water quality	Emergency situation
UNI EN ISO 19679:2020 Plastics - Determination of aerobic biodegradation of non-floating plastic materials in a seawater/sediment interface - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	Environmental management	Methodology / test methods
	Environmental management	Plastic materials
ISO 20596-2:2021 Water quality — Determination of cyclic volatile methylsiloxanes in water — Part 2: Method using liquid-liquid extraction with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Methylsiloxanes
ISO/TR 16475:2020 General practices for the repair of water-leakage cracks in concrete structures	Urban areas	Water-leakage cracks
ISO 20468-3:2020 Guidelines for performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems — Part 3: Ozone treatment technology	Water reuse	Ozone treatment
ISO 16075-1:2020 Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects — Part 1: The basis of a reuse project for irrigation	Water reuse	Irrigation
ISO 16075-2:2020 Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects — Part 2: Development of the project	Water reuse	Irrigation
ISO 10872:2020 Water and soil quality — Determination of the toxic effect of sediment and soil samples on growth, fertility and reproduction of Caenorhabditis elegans (Nematoda)	Water quality	Nematoda
ISO 22066:2020 Water quality — Determination of total cyanide — Method using segmented flow injection, in-line ultraviolet digestion analysis by gas diffusion and amperometric detection	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Cyanide
ISO 23977-1:2020 Plastics — Determination of the aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials exposed to seawater — Part 1: Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	Physical method	Plastic materials
ISO 23977-2:2020 Plastics — Determination of the aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials exposed to seawater — Part 2: Method by measuring the oxygen demand in closed respirometer	Physical method	Plastic materials
UNI EN 4426:2020 Aerospace series - Non-metallic materials - Textiles - Test method - Determination of conductivity and pH of aqueous extracts	Physical method	Textile materials
UNI EN ISO 21285:2020 Soil quality - Inhibition of reproduction of the soil mite (Hypoaspis aculeifer) by soil contaminants	Soil quality	Hypoaspis aculeifer
UNI EN ISO 21365:2020 Soil quality - Conceptual site models for potentially contaminated sites	Soil quality	Contaminated sites
ISO/IEC 30142:2020 Information technology -- Underwater acoustic sensor network (UWASN) -- Network management system overview and requirements	Society	IoT
ISO 5667-1:2020 Water quality — Sampling — Part 1: Guidance on the design of sampling programmes and sampling techniques	Water quality	Sampling
ISO 5667-10:2020 Water quality — Sampling — Part 10: Guidance on sampling of waste water	Water quality	Sampling

	Water quality	Industrial wastewater
ISO 22524:2020 Pilot plan for industrial wastewater treatment facilities in the objective of water reuse	Industrial waste water	Pilot treatment technology
ISO 22447:2019 Industrial wastewater classification	Industrial waste water	Classification
ISO 20670:2018(en) Water reuse — Vocabulary	Water reuse	Terminology
ISO 20469:2018	Water reuse	Water quality
Guidelines for water quality grade classification for water reuse	Water reuse	Classification
	Water reuse	Non potable water
ISO 20468-1:2018	Water reuse	Performance evaluation
Guidelines for performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems — Part 1: General	Water reuse	Water quality
	Water reuse	KPI
ISO 20468-2:2019	Water reuse	Enviromental performance
Guidelines for performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems — Part 2: Methodology to evaluate performance of treatment systems on the basis of greenhouse gas emissions	Water reuse	Performance evaluation
	Water reuse	GHG
ISO 20426:2018	Water reuse	Health risk
Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse	Water reuse	Non potable water
ISO 20760-1:2018	Water reuse	Water reuse
Water reuse in urban areas — Guidelines for centralized water reuse system — Part 1: Design principle of a centralized water reuse system	Water reuse	Planning
	Water reuse	Design
ISO 20760-2:2017	Water reuse	Water reuse
Water reuse in urban areas — Guidelines for centralized water reuse system — Part 2: Management of a centralized water reuse system	Water reuse	Planning
	Water reuse	Design
ISO 20761:2018	Water quality	Performance evaluation
Water reuse in urban areas — Guidelines for water reuse safety evaluation — Assessment parameters and methods	Water quality	Safety
	Water quality	KPI
ISO 6107 series	Water quality	Terminology
UNI EN ISO 5667-3:2018 Water quality — Sampling — Part 3: Preservation and handling of water sample	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Sampling
ISO 5667-5:2006 Water quality — Sampling — Part 5: Guidance on sampling of drinking water from treatment works and piped distribution systems	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Potable water
UNI EN ISO 5667-13:2011 Water quality — Sampling — Part 13: Guidance on sampling of sludges	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Sludge
	Water quality	Waste water
UNI EN ISO 5667-14:2014 Water quality — Sampling — Part 14: Guidance on quality assurance and quality control of environmental water sampling and handling	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Quality control
UNI EN ISO 5667-16:2017 Water quality — Sampling — Part 16: Guidance on biotesting of samples	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Biological test
	Water quality	Ecotoxicological test
	Water quality	Waste water
ISO 5667-21:2010 Water quality — Sampling — Part 21: Guidance on sampling of drinking water distributed by tankers or means other than distribution pipes	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Drinking water
	Water quality	Municipality
UNI EN ISO 5667-23:2011 water quality — Sampling — Part 23: Guidance on passive sampling in surface waters	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Surface water
ISO 5667-24:2016 - Water quality — Sampling — Part 24: Guidance on the auditing of water quality sampling	Water quality	Sampling
	Water quality	Audit
ISO 24511:2007	Waste water service	KPI
Activities relating to drinking water and wastewater services — Guidelines for the management of wastewater utilities and for the assessment of wastewater services	Waste water service	Terminology
	Waste water service	Utilities
ISO 24513:2019	Waste water service	Terminology
Service activities relating to drinking water supply, wastewater and stormwater systems — Vocabulary		
ISO 24516-1:2016	Waste water service	Drinking water
Guidelines for the management of assets of water supply and wastewater systems — Part 1: Drinking water distribution networks	Waste water service	Asset management
	Waste water service	Distribution network
ISO 24516-2:2019	Waste water service	Drinking water
Guidelines for the management of assets of water supply and wastewater systems — Part 2: Waterworks	Waste water service	Asset management
	Waste water service	Distribution network
ISO 24516-3:2017	Waste water service	Drinking water
Guidelines for the management of assets of water supply and wastewater systems — Part 3: Wastewater collection networks	Waste water service	Asset management
	Waste water service	Distribution network
ISO 24516-4:2019	Waste water service	Drinking water
Guidelines for the management of assets of water supply and wastewater systems — Part 4: Wastewater treatment plants, sludge treatment facilities, pumping stations, retention and detention facilities	Waste water service	Asset management
	Waste water service	Distribution network
ISO 24518:2015	Waste water service	Crisis management
Activities relating to drinking water and wastewater services — Crisis management of water utilities		
ISO/TS 24522:2019	Waste water service	Events detection
Event detection process: Guidelines for water and wastewater utilities		
ISO 24523:2017	Waste water service	KPI
Service activities relating to drinking water supply systems and wastewater systems — Guidelines for benchmarking of water utilities	Waste water service	KPI
ISO 24527:2020	Waste water service	Crisis management
Service activities relating to drinking water supply, wastewater and stormwater systems — Guidelines on alternative drinking water service provision during a crisis		
ISO/TS 24520:2017	Waste water service	Crisis management
Service activities relating to drinking water supply systems and wastewater systems — Crisis management — Good practice for technical aspects		
ISO 24512:2007	Waste water service	Asset management
Activities relating to drinking water and wastewater services — Guidelines for the management of drinking water utilities and for the assessment of drinking water services		
UNI EN 872:2005 - Water quality - Determination of suspended solids - Method by filtration through glass fibre filters	Water quality	TSS
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	KPI
EN ISO 5815-1:2019- Water quality - Determination of biochemical oxygen demand after n days (BODn) - Part 1: Dilution and seeding method with allylthiourea addition (ISO 5815-1:2019)	Water quality	BOD
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	KPI
UNI EN ISO 15681-1:2005 - Water quality - Determination of orthophosphate and total phosphorus contents by flow analysis (FIA and CFA) - Part 1: Method by flow injection analysis (FIA)	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Phosphorus
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Flow injection analysis
UNI EN ISO 15681-2:2018 Water quality -- Determination of orthophosphate and total phosphorus contents by flow analysis (FIA and CFA) Method by continuous flow analysis (CFA)	Water quality	Phosphorus
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods

	Water quality	Continuous flow analysys
	Water quality	KPI
UNI EN ISO 6878:2004 - Water quality - Determination of phosphorus - Ammonium molybdate spectrometric method	Water quality	Phosphorus
	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 10695:2006 - Water quality - Determination of selected organic nitrogen and phosphorus compounds - Gas chromatographic methods	Water quality	Phosphorus
	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Organic nitrogen
UNI EN ISO 7027-1:2016 - Water quality - Determination of turbidity - Part 1: Quantitative methods	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Turbidity
UNI EN ISO 7027-2:2019 - Water quality - Determination of turbidity - Part 2: Semi-quantitative methods for the assessment of transparency of waters	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Turbidity
UNI EN ISO 11732:2005 - Water quality - Determination of ammonium nitrogen - Method by flow analysis (CFA and FIA) and spectrometric detection	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Ammonium nitrogen
UNI EN ISO 9963-1:1998 - Water quality - Determination of alkalinity - Determination of total and composite alkalinity	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Alkalinity
UNI EN ISO 9963-2:1998 - Water quality - Determination of alkalinity - Determination of carbonate alkalinity	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Carbonate alkalinity
UNI EN 27888:1995 - Water quality. Determination of electrical conductivity.	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Conductivity
UNI EN ISO 12020:2002 - Water quality - Determination of aluminium - Atomic absorption spectrometric methods	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Aluminium
UNI EN 1622:2006 - Water quality - Determination of the threshold odour number (TON) and threshold flavour number (TFN)	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Odour
UNI EN ISO 9308-1:2017 - Water quality - Enumeration of Escherichia coli and coliform bacteria - Part 1: Membrane filtration method for waters with low bacterial background flora	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Pathogens
	Water quality	E. coli
UNI EN ISO 9308-2:2014 - Water quality - Enumeration of Escherichia coli and coliform bacteria - Part 2: Most probable number method (ISO 9308-2:2012)	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Pathogens
	Water quality	E. coli
UNI EN ISO 9308-3:2001 - Water quality - Detection and enumeration of Escherichia coli and coliform bacteria in surface and waste water - Miniaturized method (Most Probable Number) by inoculation in liquid medium.	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Pathogens
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	E. coli
UNI EN ISO 11731:2017 Water quality - Enumeration of Legionella	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Pathogens
	Water quality	Legionella
UNI EN ISO 6341:2013 - Water quality - Determination of the inhibition of the mobility of Daphnia magna Straus (Cladocera, Crustacea) - Acute toxicity test	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Toxicity
	Water quality	Daphnia Magna
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 7887:2012 - Water quality - Examination and determination of colour	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Colour
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 8199:2018 - Water quality - General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations by culture	Water quality	Microbiological examination
	Water quality	Pathogens
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 19458:2006 - Water quality - Sampling for microbiological analysis	Water quality	Sampling
ISO 10705-3:2003 Water quality — Detection and enumeration of bacteriophages — Part 3: Validation of methods for concentration of bacteriophages from water	Water quality	Performance evaluation
	Water quality	Pathogens
ISO/TS 15923-2:2017 - Water quality -- Determination of selected parameters by discrete analysis systems Chromium(VI), fluoride, total alkalinity, total hardness, calcium, magnesium, iron, iron(III), manganese and aluminium with photometric detection	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Iron
	Water quality	Manganese
	Water quality	Aluminium
	Water quality	Calcium
	Water quality	Magnesium
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 10304-1:2009 - Water quality - Determination of dissolved anions by liquid chromatography of ions - Part 1: Determination of bromide, chloride, fluoride, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate and sulfate	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Detergent
	Water quality	Anions
UNI ISO 9964-1:2009 - Water quality - Determination of sodium and potassium - Part 1: Determination of sodium by atomic absorption spectrometry	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Sodium
	Water quality	Potassium
UNI ISO 9964-2:2009 - Water quality - Determination of sodium and potassium - Part 2: Determination of potassium by atomic absorption spectrometry	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Sodium
	Water quality	Potassium
UNI ISO 8288:2009 - Water quality - Determination of cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, cadmium and lead - Flame atomic absorption spectrometric methods	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Copper
	Water quality	Nickel
	Water quality	Cobalt
	Water quality	Cadmium
	Water quality	Zinc
	Water quality	Lead

UNI EN ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework (ISO 14040:2006)	Environmental management	LCA
UNI EN ISO 14044:2018 Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines	Environmental management	LCA
UNI ISO/TS 14072:2015 Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines for organizational life cycle assessment	Environmental management	LCA
UNI EN ISO 14046:2016 Environmental management - Water footprint - Principles, requirements and guidelines	Environmental management	LCA
ISO/TR 14073:2017 - Environmental management — Water footprint — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046	Environmental management	LCA
UNI EN 16101:2013 - Water quality - Guidance standard on interlaboratory comparison studies for ecological assessment	Water quality	Interlaboratory
	Water quality	Audit
UNI EN ISO 14911:2001 - Water quality - Determination of dissolved Li+, Na+, NH4+, K+, Mn2+, Ca2+, Mg2+, Sr2+ and Ba2+ using ion chromatography - Method for water and waste water	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Lithium
	Water quality	Sodium
	Water quality	Ammonium
	Water quality	Potassium
	Water quality	Manganese
	Water quality	Calcium
	Water quality	Magnesium
	Water quality	Strontium
	Water quality	Barium
UNI EN ISO 7899-1:2001 - Water quality - Detection and enumeration of intestinal enterococci - Miniaturized method (Most Probable Number) for surface and waste water.	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Intestinal enterococci
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Pathogens
UNI 11757:2019 - Determination of Total Phosphorous and P-orthophosphate in waste, natural and drinking waters with small-scale sealed-tube method	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Phosphorus
ISO 17381:2003 - Water quality -- Selection and application of ready-to-use test kit methods in water analysis	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 15839:2006 - Water quality - On-line sensors/ analysing equipment for water - Specifications and performance tests	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI EN ISO 21253-2:2019 - Water quality - Multi-compound class methods - Part 2: Criteria for the quantitative determination of organic substances using a multi-compound class analytical method	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
	Water quality	Organic
UNI EN ISO 10523:2012 - Water quality - Determination of pH	Water quality	KPI
	Water quality	Methodology / test methods
UNI ISO 37120:2019 - Sustainable cities and communities -- Indicators for city services and quality of life	Urban areas	KPI
	Urban areas	Sustainable cities
UNI ISO 37123:2020 - Sustainable cities and communities -- Indicators for resilient cities	Urban areas	KPI
	Urban areas	Methodology / test methods
	Urban areas	Sustainable cities
UNI ISO 20400:2017 - Sustainable procurement -- Guidance	Public administration	KPI
	Public administration	Methodology / test methods
	Public administration	Sustainable procurement
UNI/PdR 18:2016 - Social responsibility in organizations - Guidance to the application of UNI ISO 26000	Society	KPI
	Society	Social Responsibility
UNI ISO 26000:2010 - Guidance on social responsibility	Society	KPI
	Society	Social Responsibility
CEN GUIDE 4 Guide for addressing environmental issues in product standards	Environmental management	Products
CEN-CENELEC Guide 33 Guide for addressing environmental issues in testing standards (includes Checklist)	Environmental management	Laboratory
UNI EN ISO 14852:2018 Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in an aqueous medium - Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide	Water quality	Carbon dioxide
		Plastic biodegradation
CEN/TR 16928:2016 Guidance for the implementation of environmental aspects in product standards and system standards in the field of wastewater engineering	Environmental management	Waste water
CWA 17031:2016 Sustainable integrated water use & treatment in process industries - a practical guidance (SustainWATER)	Environmental management	Water reuse

Appendix 2 - List of the standards (46) firstly spotted for the topic "technology" [section 3.2.2]

REFERENCE w/ link	Standard title	Technology	Area	Keyword
UNI EN ISO 20456:2020	Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits - Guidance for the use of electromagnetic flowmeters for conductive liquids	High-voltage generator	(Pulsed) Electronic field	Electromagnetic flowmeters
UNI EN ISO 16526-1:2020	Non-destructive testing - Measurement and evaluation of the X-ray tube voltage - Part 1: Voltage divider method	High-voltage generator	High voltage	X-ray - measurement
UNI EN 12954:2019	General principles of cathodic protection of buried or immersed onshore metallic structures	High-voltage generator	High voltage	Cathodic protection
ISO/TS 10832:2009	Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on mycorrhizal fungi -- Spore germination test	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 20963:2005	Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on insect larvae (<i>Oxythreya funesta</i>) -- Determination of acute toxicity	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 11268-1:2012	Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on earthworms Determination of acute toxicity to <i>Eisenia fetida</i>/<i>Eisenia andrei</i>	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 20963:2011	Soil quality - Effects of pollutants on insect larvae (<i>Oxythreya funesta</i>) - Determination of acute toxicity	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 11268-3:2014	Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on earthworms Guidance on the determination of effects in field situations	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 11269-1:2012	Soil quality -- Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora Method for the measurement of inhibition of root growth	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 17126:2005	Soil quality -- Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora -- Screening test for emergence of lettuce seedlings (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.)	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 11269-2:2012	Soil quality -- Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora Effects of contaminated soil on the emergence and early growth of higher plants	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 11268-2:2012	Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on earthworms Determination of effects on reproduction of <i>Eisenia fetida</i>/<i>Eisenia andrei</i>	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 15952:2018	Soil quality -- Effects of pollutants on juvenile land snails (<i>Helicidae</i>) -- Determination of the effects on growth by soil contamination	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
ISO 21479:2019	Soil quality -- Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora -- Leaf fatty acid composition of plants used to assess soil quality	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 21479:2020	Soil quality - Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora - Leaf fatty acid composition of plants to assess soil quality	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 15952:2018	Soil quality - Effects of pollutants on juvenile land snails (<i>Helicidae</i>) - Determination of the effects on growth by soil contamination	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 11268-1:2015	Soil quality - Effects of pollutants on earthworms - Part 1: Determination of acute toxicity to <i>Eisenia fetida</i>/<i>Eisenia andrei</i>	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 11268-2:2015	Soil quality - Effects of pollutants on earthworms - Part 2: Determination of effects on reproduction of <i>Eisenia fetida</i>/<i>Eisenia andrei</i>	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 11268-3:2015	Soil quality - Effects of pollutants on earthworms - Part 3: Guidance on the determination of effects in field situations	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 11269-1:2013	Soil quality - Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora - Part 1: Method for the measurement of inhibition of root growth	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN ISO 11269-2:2013	Soil quality - Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora - Part 2: Effects of contaminated soil on the emergence and early growth of higher plants	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN 12873-3:2019	Influence of materials on water intended for human consumption - Influence due to migration - Part 3: Test method for ion exchange and adsorbent resins	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Water quality
UNI EN ISO 23611-1:2018	Soil quality - Sampling of soil invertebrates - Part 1: Hand-sorting and extraction of earthworms	High-voltage generator	Emerging pollutants	Soil quality
UNI EN 15074:2014	Chemicals used for treatment of swimming pool water - Ozone	High-voltage generator	Ozone	Water treatment
UNI EN 1278:2010	Chemicals used for treatment of water intended for human consumption - Ozone	High-voltage generator	Ozone	Water treatment
ISO 20304-1:2020	Fine bubble technology -- Water treatment applications Test method for evaluating ozone fine bubble water generating systems by the decolorization of methylene blue	High-voltage generator	Ozone	Water treatment
ISO 20468-3:2020	Guidelines for performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems Ozone treatment technology	High-voltage generator	Ozone	Water reuse
ISO 21793:2020	Water quality -- Determination of total organic carbon (TOC), dissolved organic carbon (DOC), total bound nitrogen (TNb), dissolved bound nitrogen (DNb), total bound phosphorus (TPb) and dissolved bound phosphorus (DPb) after wet chemical catalysed ozone hydroxyl radical oxidation (COHR)	High-voltage generator	Ozone	Water quality
UNI EN 12915-2:2009	Products used for the treatment of water intended for human consumption - Granular activated carbon - Part 2: Reactivated granular activated carbon	Advanced carbon adsorption	Activated carbons	Water treatment
UNI EN 12915-1:2009	Products used for the treatment of water intended for human consumption - Granular activated carbon - Part 1: Virgin granular activated carbon	Advanced carbon adsorption	Activated carbons	Water treatment
ISO 8192:2007	Water quality -- Test for inhibition of oxygen consumption by activated sludge for carbonaceous and ammonium oxidation	Advanced carbon adsorption	Activated carbons	Water quality
UNI EN 15799:2010	Products used for treatment of swimming pool water - Powdered activated carbon	Advanced carbon adsorption	Activated carbons	Water treatment
UNI EN 12903:2009	Chemicals used for the treatment of water intended for human consumption - Powdered activated carbon	Advanced carbon adsorption	Activated carbons	Water treatment
UNI EN ISO 8192:2007	Water quality - Test for inhibition of oxygen consumption by activated sludge for carbonaceous and ammonium oxidation	Advanced carbon adsorption	Activated carbons	Water quality
UNI CEN/TS 16981:2017	Photocatalysis - Glossary of terms	Advanced carbon adsorption photocatalysis	Photocatalysis	Glossary
UNI EN 17120:2019	Photocatalysis - Water purification - Performance of photocatalytic materials by measurement of phenol degradation	Advanced carbon adsorption photocatalysis	Photocatalysis	Water treatment
UNI CEN/TS 16599:2014	Photocatalysis - Irradiation conditions for testing photocatalytic properties of semiconducting materials and the measurement of these conditions	Advanced carbon adsorption photocatalysis	Photocatalysis	Semiconductors properties
UNI EN 16845-1:2017	Photocatalysis - Anti-soiling chemical activity using adsorbed organics under solid/solid conditions - Part 1: Dyes on porous surfaces	Advanced carbon adsorption photocatalysis	Photocatalysis	Materials performance
ISO 20814:2019	Nanotechnologies — Testing the photocatalytic activity of nanoparticles for NADH oxidation	Advanced carbon adsorption photocatalysis	Photocatalysis	Nanoparticles
ISO 23044:2020	Guidelines for softening and desalination of industrial wastewater for reuse	Aalborg University: membrane distillation and nanofiltration	Nanofiltration	Industrial wastewater
ISO/TS 18110:2015	Nanotechnologies — Vocabularies for science, technology and innovation indicators	Aalborg University: membrane distillation and nanofiltration	Nanofiltration	Glossary
ISO/TR 11044:2008	Water quality -- Scientific and technical aspects of batch algae growth inhibition tests	Bio-algae denitrification	Algae	Water quality
UNI EN ISO 8692:2012	Water quality - Fresh water algal growth inhibition test with unicellular green algae	Bio-algae denitrification	Algae	Water quality
UNI EN 17211:2019	Water quality - Guidance on mapping of seagrasses and macroalgae in the eu littoral zone	Bio-algae denitrification	Algae	Water quality

ISO 8692:2012	Water quality -- Fresh water algal growth inhibition test with unicellular green algae	Bio-algae denitrification	Algae	Water quality
UNI EN ISO 10253:2017	Water quality - Marine algal growth inhibition test with Skeletonema sp. and Phaeodactylum tricornutum	Bio-algae denitrification	Algae	Water quality